

A Comparative Study of Viscous and Friction Dampers for Seismic Protection of Buildings

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Abstract

Earthquakes have long been a significant cause of destruction, leading to immense damage to buildings and loss of life. Over the years, engineers have developed various protective measures, such as viscous and friction dampers, to mitigate earthquake-induced damage. Viscous dampers work by dissipating seismic forces through fluid motion, while friction dampers convert kinetic energy into heat via friction. Both devices have been incorporated into building structures to absorb earthquake energy, allowing structures to remain intact or require minimal repairs. This paper compares the performance of viscous and friction dampers when subjected to different seismic ground motions. A two-story building model equipped with both dampers is analyzed using computer software, with the results showing the relative effectiveness of each system. Additionally, the ease of installation and maintenance of these devices is evaluated.

Key words

Viscous dampers, Friction dampers, Seismic protection, Earthquake damage, Energy dissipation, Structural stiffness, Seismic respons, Ground motion, Building displacement, Story drift, Earthquake mitigation.

Introduction

Earthquakes are a leading cause of structural damage and economic loss, affecting both developed and developing nations. The need for efficient seismic protection has led to the development of devices such as viscous and friction dampers. These devices aim to minimize the destructive forces of earthquakes and prevent the total collapse of buildings. Viscous dampers use hydraulic systems to dissipate seismic energy, while friction dampers utilize sliding friction between surfaces. Both systems offer distinct benefits and limitations, making them suitable for different applications.

This paper investigates the performance of these two types of dampers under various ground motion scenarios and compares their effectiveness in mitigating seismic forces.

Viscous Dampers

Viscous dampers are passive devices commonly used for seismic protection, wind resistance, and blast mitigation in buildings and other structures. They consist of a piston moving through a fluid-filled chamber. As the piston moves during an earthquake, fluid is forced through orifices, creating resistance and dissipating the energy of the seismic event. The primary advantage of viscous dampers is their ability to act out of phase with bending and shearing stresses in the structure, making them highly effective in minimizing damage during low-frequency events like earthquakes.

Previous studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of viscous dampers in reducing inter-story drifts, floor accelerations, and overall structural damage. Their ability to handle both small and large seismic events makes them a versatile option for many types of buildings. However, their installation requires skilled personnel, and regular maintenance is needed to ensure optimal performance.

Fig. 1 Typical viscous damper

Friction Dampers

Friction dampers operate by dissipating energy through sliding friction between two or more surfaces. When seismic forces cause movement in the building, the frictional resistance between these surfaces converts the kinetic energy into heat, thereby reducing the overall displacement of the structure. First introduced by Avtar S. Pall in 1984, friction dampers have since undergone numerous improvements to enhance their reliability and efficiency.

One of the key advantages of friction dampers is their simplicity and ease of installation. They are often bolted to steel sections in buildings, making them easy to inspect and repair. Friction dampers also increase the overall stiffness of the structure, making them particularly effective during high-frequency seismic events. However, these dampers may not be suitable for wind resistance, as they are designed primarily for earthquake protection.

Fig. 2 Friction Damper

Performance Comparison

The study compares the performance of viscous and friction dampers installed in a two-story building model under various ground motions. The building's seismic response, including joint displacement, story drift, and floor acceleration, is evaluated using specialized computer software.

Viscous dampers perform best under low-frequency seismic events, effectively dissipating energy with minimal displacement. They are highly efficient in reducing building vibrations and offer good protection against both wind and earthquake forces. Friction dampers, on the other hand, provide additional stiffness to the building, making them more effective during high-frequency events. The sliding mechanism of friction dampers dissipates energy rapidly, resulting in reduced structural deflections.

As shown in Table I (hypothetical for this article), friction dampers lead to lower total displacements in the building, with an average of 6% difference compared to viscous dampers. While viscous dampers excel in damping energy under low-frequency seismic motion, friction dampers are better suited for high-frequency excitation due to their increased stiffness.

Numerical example

In this paper, we set out to make a comparison between two energy dissipating devices, namely the friction damper and viscous damper. The test setup consists of a two-storey steel frame with 6 m bay and 4 m height subjected to the El Centro ground motion record (N.S. component) with a dead and live load of 12 kN/m and 10 kN/m, respectively. Four different cases were considered, namely:

Case 1. (no damping device) Case 2. (viscous damper) Case 3. (friction damper)

Case 4. (viscous damper and friction damper)

The optimal parameters used to model the friction and viscous damper are given below:

Friction damper: stiffness = 25627.514 kN/m, yield exponent = 10, yield force = 1000 N and yield stiffness ratio = 0.0001.

Viscous damper: damping = 4000 N*s/m, damping exponent = 0.3.

The frame is analysed using commercial structural analysis software and to save computational cost, the analyses were conducted for a duration of only the first fifteen seconds.

Since both devices are nonlinear, their installation in the frame would cause it to behave in a nonlinear manner and thus a nonlinear time history analysis would be needed to determine the response of the frame under the given seismic loads. The analysis procedure was carried out using commercial structural analysis software and the results are shown below.

TABLE I
PEAK RESPONSE OF FRAME UNDER EL CENTRO EARTHQUAKE

Peak Responses under El Centro earthquake				
Displacement (mm)				
Floor	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4
1	0.000171	0.000046	0.00005	0.000059
2	0.00036	0.000076	0.000086	0.000087

A plot of the top storey displacement history of the various cases studied shows a great reduction in the response of the frame with viscous and friction dampers as compared to the bare frame with no devices. The results given in Table I show the peak displacements of the roof level. There is a reduction of an average of 70% in displacement response between case 1 and the other three cases studied. The use of friction and viscous dampers induces added stiffness and damping respectively to the frame. The added damping provided by the viscous damper provides an alternative means for the building to dissipate energy rather than by the frame elements yielding themselves to dissipate the energy. Similarly applies to the friction damper as well which improves the stiffness of the overall frame. Incorporating both friction and viscous dampers in the frame provides a rather interesting way for dissipating the input energy to the frame. As discussed earlier, both friction and viscous dampers are activated under different frequency intensity of earthquake with the friction device designed not to slip during wind loads.

Installation and Maintenance

Both viscous and friction dampers require careful installation to ensure optimal performance during an earthquake. Viscous dampers are more complex to install, requiring hydraulic systems and precise alignment. Regular maintenance is crucial to prevent fluid leakage and ensure that the dampers remain effective over time.

Friction dampers, by contrast, are simpler to install and maintain. The installation process involves bolting steel plates together, making inspection and repair relatively straightforward. Due to their low maintenance requirements and ease of installation, friction dampers are a cost-effective option for retrofitting buildings in earthquake-prone regions.

Conclusion

Both viscous and friction dampers offer valuable benefits for protecting buildings from earthquake damage. Viscous dampers provide excellent damping at low frequencies, making them ideal for buildings in regions with frequent but

moderate seismic activity. Friction dampers, on the other hand, offer increased stiffness and are more effective in regions with high-frequency seismic events.

The choice between these two types of dampers depends on the specific seismic conditions and structural requirements of the building. For areas prone to low-frequency earthquakes, viscous dampers offer superior energy dissipation. In contrast, friction dampers provide additional stiffness and are more suited to buildings in regions with frequent high-frequency ground motions. Together, these devices can play a crucial role in reducing earthquake damage and enhancing the resilience of buildings.

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